

A STUDY ON WORKERS PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT IN RYDON INDUSTRIES PRIVATE LIMITED, COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

This study examines the workers' participation management in Rydon Industries Private Limited, Coimbatore. The primary objective is to determine the overall satisfaction and commitment level of employees in the company. A comprehensive analysis of the Human Resource department's working methods and functions was conducted. A sample size of 124 was selected, and data was collected through a structured questionnaire, analyzed using Percentage Analysis, Correlation, and Chi-square techniques with the aid of SPSS software. The study reveals the importance of employee participation in management decision-making, leading to increased job satisfaction, commitment, and productivity. The findings suggest that effective communication, involvement in decision-making, and recognition of employee contributions are essential for fostering a positive work environment. The study recommends organizations prioritize employee participation in management to enhance overall performance and employee well-being.

Key Words: Worker Participation, Management Decision-Making, Employee Satisfaction

Introduction:

Worker's participation in management is an essential ingredient of Industrial democracy. The concept of workers' participation in management is based on Human Relations approach to Management which brought about a new set of values to labor and management. Traditionally the concept of Workers' Participation in Management (WPM) refers to participation of non-managerial employees in the decision-making process of the organization. Workers' participation is also known as 'labor participation' or 'employee participation' in management. In Germany it is known as co-determination while in Yugoslavia it is known as self-management. The International Labor Organization has been encouraging member nations to promote the scheme of Workers' Participation in Management. Workers' participation in management implies mental and emotional involvement of workers in the management of Enterprise. It is considered as a mechanism where workers have a say in the decision-making.

Definition:

According to Keith Davis, Participation refers to the mental and emotional involvement of a person in a group situation which encourages him to contribute to group goals and share the responsibility of achievement. According to Walpole, Participation in Management gives the worker a sense of importance, pride and accomplishment; it gives him the freedom of opportunity for self expression; a feeling of belongingness with the place of work and a sense of workmanship and creativity. The concept of workers' participation in management encompasses the following:

- It provides scope for employees in decision-making of the organization.
- The participation may be at the shop level, departmental level or at the top level.
- The participation includes the willingness to share the responsibility of the organization by the workers.

Features of WPM:

- Participation means mental and emotional involvement rather than mere physical presence.
- Workers participate in management not as individuals but collectively as a group through their representatives.
- Workers' participation in management may be formal or informal. In both the cases it is a system of communication and consultation whereby employees express their opinions and contribute to managerial decisions.

There can be 5 levels of Management Participation or WPM:

- **Information Participation:**

It ensures that employees are able to receive information and express their views pertaining to the matter of general economic importance.

- **Consultative Importance:**

Here workers are consulted on the matters of employee welfare such as work, safety and health.

However, final decision always rests with the top-level management, as employees' views are only advisory in nature.

- **Associative participation:**

It is an extension of consultative participation as management here is under the moral obligation to accept and implement the unanimous decisions of the employees. Under this method the managers and workers jointly take decisions.

- **Administrative Participation:**

It ensures greater share of workers' participation in discharge of managerial functions. Here, decisions already taken by the management come to employees, preferably with alternatives for administration and employees have to select the best from those for implementation.

- **Decisive Participation:**
Highest level of participation where decisions are jointly taken on the matters.

Objectives of WPM:

- To establish Industrial Democracy.
- To build the most dynamic Human Resources.
- To satisfy the workers' social and esteem needs.
- To strengthen labour-management co-operation and thus maintain Industrial peace and harmony.
- To promote increased productivity for the advantage of the organization, workers and the society at large.
- Its psychological objective is to secure full recognition of the workers.

Implications of Workers Participation in Management:

The implications of workers' participation in management have been summarized by the International Labour Organization thus:

- Workers have ideas which can be useful
- Upward communication facilitates sound decision-making. Workers may accept decisions better if they participate in them.
- Workers may work more intelligently if they are informed about the reasons for and the intention of decisions that are taken in a participative atmosphere.
- Workers may work harder if they share in decisions that affect them.
- Worker's participation may foster a more cooperative attitude amongst workers and management thus raising efficiency by improving team spirit and reducing the loss of efficiency arising from industrial disputes.
- Worker's participation may act as a spur to managerial efficiency.

Worker's participation in management has assumed great importance these days because of the following advantages:

- **Increased Organization Balance:**

If worker are invited to share in organizational problems, and to work towards common solutions, a greater degree of organizational balance occurs because of decreased misunderstanding of individual and group conflict. Participation leads to increased understanding throughout the organization. People learn that others have problems beside themselves.

- **Higher Productivity:**

Increased productivity is possible only when there exists fullest co-operation between labor and management. It has been empirically tested that poor 'labor management relations' do not encourage the workers to contribute anything more than the minimum desirable to retain their jobs. Thus, participation of workers in management is essential to increase industrial productivity.

- **Increased Commitment:**

An important prerequisite for forging greater commitment is the individual's involvement and opportunity to express himself. Participation allows individuals to express themselves at the work place rather than being absorbed into a complex system of rules, procedures and systems. If an individual knows that he can express his opinion and ideas, a personal sense of gratification and involvement takes place within him. This, in turn, fortifies his identification with the organization resulting in greater commitment.

- **Industrial Democracy:**

Participation helps to usher in an era of democracy in industry. It is based on the principle of recognition of the human factor. It tends to reduce class conflict between capital and labor. It also serves as a support to political democracy.

- **Development of Individuals:**

Participation enhances individual creativity and response to job challenges. Individuals are given an opportunity to direct their initiative and creativity towards the objectives of the group. This facilitates individual growth. 8. Less resistance to change: when changes are arbitrarily introduced from above without explanation, subordinates tend to feel insecure and take counter measures aimed at sabotage of innovations. But when they have participated in the decision making process, they have had an opportunity to be heard. They know what to expect and why. Their resistance to change is reduced. The realization of workers' need for participation in the management is influenced by the following factors:

- Technology adoption leading to complexity in production process calls for increased worker cooperation.
- Employees are no longer treated as subservient but are treated as equals.
- Growing influence of union prevents exploitation of employees by management.
- There are regulations and legislations that facilitate increased workers participation in management.
- Higher levels of productivity and efficiency can only come through motivated and committed employee

Statement of the Problem:

Worker's participation in management is the participation of the workers in decision- making as well as various important aspects of an organization, which has been accepted as a fundamental concomitant of harmonious labor management relations. The need for their researcher to study "worker's participation in management" is to find out the workers' need level.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objective:

The main objective is "A Study on workers participation management on Rydon industries private limited, Coimbatore."

Secondary Objective:

- To know the opinion of respondents towards Workers' participation in Management.
- To study the Management responses to the extent to the influence company policies
- To study the popular methods of workers participation in management

- To know the opinion of respondents towards their working conditions and their Job Satisfaction.
- To create in employees a sense of participation in industry and to improve the working and living conditions of employees.
- To promote better understanding between labours and management on the various issues of the organizations.
- To study the employees facing the challenges in participation of management.

Need of the Study:

This study's main objective is to give an improved perspective of the HR Practice, Workers' Participation in Management with respect to Rydon industries. Besides, it also aims to study how workers' involvement helps their motivation level and its following impact on industrial relations. This research will help the researchers to fill in the gap and provide further literature as an addition to assist them in their future research. This research study will provide the most recent implications in respect to examining the relationship between employees and employers and how workers' closer involvement helps them fulfil their interests. Moreover, this research also aims to give beneficial information to the Rydon Industrialists about how WPM increases the employee's motivation level and raises the production capacity. This will also aid the employers to maintain cordial relations with their employees and benefit the working of various industries.

Scope of the Study:

Workers' participation can serve a number of purposes, all geared to achieve organizational effectiveness and the satisfaction of the employees. Workers' participation can encourage communication at all levels. Joint decision making ensure that there will be minimum industrial conflict and economic growth can be free from distracting strike. Participation is possible at all levels of management. It depends upon the nature of functions; the strength of the workers, varieties of depends upon the nature of function, the strength of the worker, varieties of departments, attitudes of trade unions and the management.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Null Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significance between the experience of the respondents and involvement in management decision making.

Alternative Hypothesis:

H₁: There is significance between the experience of the respondents and involvement in management decision making.

Research Design:

A research design is the basic frame work or plan for a study that guides the collection of data and analysis of the data in employee surveys this descriptive research design is adopted in data collection and analysis.

Research Methodology:

Meaning:

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In it we study the various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying his research problem along with the logic behind them. It is necessary for the researcher to know not only the research methods techniques but also the methodology. It refers to process used to collect information and data for the purpose of making business decision. The methodology may include publication research, interview, surveys and other research techniques, and could include both present and historical information.

Definition:

According to industrial research institute in research methodology, research always tries to search the given question systematically in our own way and find out all the answers till conclusion. If research does not work systematically on problem, there would be less possibility to find out the final result. For finding or exploring research questions, a researcher faces lot of problems that can be effectively resolved with using correct research methodology.

Descriptive Research:

Descriptive research can be explained as a statement of affairs as they are at present with the researcher having no control over variable. Moreover, "descriptive research may be characterized as simply the attempt to determine, describe or identify what is, while analytical research attempts to establish why it is that way or how it came to be.

Sampling Method:

The sampling technique used in this study is "convenience sampling" when the population element for inclusion in the sample is based on the ease of access. It can be called as convenience

Sampling Design:

The sampling design being used for this study is convenient sampling size selected was 124 employees.

Method of Data Collection:

This research has used both primary and secondary for the study.

Primary Data:

Primary data was collected through direct interaction with employees. The employees are interviewed by giving a questionnaire the filled in questionnaire leads to the collection of primary data.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data termed as reference data. The data is obtained form already existing information, information from the personnel department's reports, and welfare department company journals, yearbooks, website etc.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

Collected data were arranged as per the tabulation, chart, and satisfied tools such as:

- Simple Percentage analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Period of the Study:

The duration taken by the researcher for the data collection and analysis regarding the employees engage of 3 Months.

Area of the Study:

The research on the title was done in the area of human resources management where the employees workers area in Rydon industries pvt.ltd at Coimbatore.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is confined only to 124 respondents among the sample size was considered as enough for the study by the researcher.
- Due to work pressure and the working environment, employees did not have sufficient time so that couldn't give proper response to the queries.
- The research has been conducted only in steel industries. So result would not reflect all other mills of Coimbatore district and cannot be generalized.

Company Profile:

Rydon is one of India's leading power transmission solution providers that cater to the needs of various industrial sectors. The basis of our consistent growth has been the long-term relationship with our select clientele by offering them nothing but the best. Over the past two decades, our manufacturing capabilities have increased over 160 times. Rydon has a well-equipped, state-of-the-art 60,000+ sq. manufacturing plant that works very closely with our Research & Development facility. Headquartered in Coimbatore, we provide cutting edge manufacturing solutions, while addressing the business needs across domains and at every stage of product life-cycle development. We export to major countries like China, Japan, USA, Netherlands, UK, France and Italy to name a few.

Rydon is Built on Reliability (Quality, Cost, On-Time Delivery):

- We adhere to international quality standards and processes while ensuring rigorous quality control checks.
- We deploy a team of highly qualified, experienced engineers and skilled workers and invest in state-of-the-art infrastructure to produce the product cost-effectively.

Product Profile:

Chain Coupling:

Constructed of two-strand chains and two sprockets. Can be connected and separated without moving the equipment by winding the chains over and removing them from the sprockets.

Body Construction:

The body consists of two dedicated sprockets with hardened teeth and two-strand roller chains.

Nylon Gear Couplings:

Nylon couplings are compact and require no lubrication. They operate over a wide temperature range at speeds up to 5000 RPM and are effectively used in applications such as Motor/ Generator sets, pump sets and many lights to medium duty industrial coupling applications. No lubrications are ever required, eliminating the need for seals. The resilient nature of nylon material makes the contact of the hubs and sleeves almost frictionless.

Jaw Coupling:

RYDON jaw couplings are characterized by small dimensions, low weight and low mass moments of inertia yet transmit high torques. Running quality and service life of the coupling are improved by accurate all-over machining. Their application is ideal for transmitting torque while damping torsional vibrations and absorbing shocks produced by the uneven operation of certain prime movers.

Performance:

In contrast to other flexible couplings, the intermediate members of which are subject to bending stress and are therefore prone to earlier wear, the flexible teeth of RYDON jaw couplings are subject to pressure only.

Pin Bush Coupling:

The function of a flexible coupling is to transmit torque from one shaft to another and is particularly use full in cases where limited misalignment may occur and also to absorb shock loads. The RYDON Pin Bush Coupling of the cushioned drive type transmits the torque through high tensile steel bolts to the machine input shaft. Highly developed rubbers components are used in bushes in absorb loads, tensional vibrations and slight misalignments

Shaft-Hub-Connections:

Frictional shaft-hub-connections are standard machine elements used to connect shafts and hubs. They are capable of transmitting Torque, axial forces, radial forces and bending moments.

Shrink Discs and Cone Clamping Elements:

Among the frictional shaft-hub-connections Shrink Discs and Cone Clamping Elements take an important position. By tightening clamping screws conical surfaces are pulled together generating radial forces

Sprocket Reliability:

System Performance depends on proper chain-sprocket interaction, which means your choice for sprockets can drive your operations success. Make the right and easy choice with sprockets from Rydon.

Taper Bush:

The Taper Lock bush, also referred to as a Taper bush or Taper Fit bush, is a locking mechanism commonly used in Power Transmission Drives for locating pulleys, sprockets, and couplings to shafts. The Taper Lock bush is pre-bored and keyed to match the required shaft and keyway diameters. The outside of the bush is tapered to match the component bore that is to be located on the shaft.

Torque Limiter:

RYDON torque limiter is a protective device that limits torque transmitted in a drive system by tripping when the torque transmitted exceeds a preset value as a result of shock loads, over loads, or machine jams. It automatically re-engages when the overload torque has passed, no resetting is required. RYDON torque limiter prevents machine damage and eliminates costly downtime. The RYDON torque limiter utilizes spring loaded friction surfaces for its operations; slip torque is present by adjustment of the spring force.

Organization Chart:

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The survey of the project has been done by collecting the data from the employees of Rydon industries, in order to achieve the scope of the Project, thus those collected data were analyzed with statistical tools and interpreted.

Opportunities for Professional Growth:

Impact of Participation on Industrial Relations:

Influence Company Policy:

**Workers Participation for Increasing Productivity:
Chi-Square Analysis:**

Workers Participation for Opportunities for Professional Growth:

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Excellent	27	24.8	2.2
Good	34	24.8	9.2
Average	43	24.8	18.2
Sometimes	13	24.8	-11.8
Poor	7	24.8	-17.8
Total	124		

Your Participation on Industrial Relation:

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	49	24.8	24.2

Agree	46	24.8	21.2
Neutral	10	24.8	-14.8
Disagree	11	24.8	-13.8
Strongly Disagree	8	24.8	-16.8
Total	124		

Test Statistics:

	Workers Participation for Opportunities for Professional Growth	Your Participation on Industrial Relation
Chi-Square	35.355 ^a	69.629 ^a
Df	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 24.8.

Correlation:

Correlations			
		Workers Participation for Increasing Productivity	Organizational Culture and Employee Participation
Workers Participation for Increasing Productivity	Pearson Correlation	1	.908**
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
	N	124	124
Organizational Culture and Employee Participation	Pearson Correlation	.908**	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	
	N	124	124

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Suggestions:

- The work environment should be congenial enough to motivate workers to give whole-hearted co-operation with a view to ensuring its efficient operation. Both the workers and management should have complete faith in the efficacy of the scheme and should pool their talents and resources, and demonstrate their will to work for the achieving of their goals.
- The participation should be real. The issues related to major strategies, product diversification, the evaluation of costs, the human resources development and the expansion of markets should also be brought under the jurisdiction of the participating bodies.
- The system of participation must be complementary to the collective bargaining process. The form, coverage, extent and levels of participation should be in the interest of the parties concerned. The objective to be achieved should not be unrealistically high, vague or ambiguous but be achievable, clear and taught to all participants.
- For the effectiveness of workers participation scheme, participation must be based on mutual trust and confidence. Hence attempts to enforce it by law or compulsion would defeat its basic purpose.
- The management should design a proper system so that the effectiveness of the schemes may be assessed periodically, and, if required, the changes may be made to make the scheme more advantageous for all the parties.

Conclusion:

The study helped the researcher to know about the factors that contribute to Workers' participation in management and relationship between management and employees. The employer and employee relationship in the company is very strong due to the Workers' participation in management. Management should be prepared to give all information connected with the working of the industry and labour should handle that information with full confidence and responsibility. The workers should become aware of their responsibilities. The leaders should initiate this in them. Similarly, the top management should make the lower echelons to show a new attitude in the light of the new relationship. Modern scholars are of the mind that the old adage "a worker is a worker, a manager is a manager; never the twain shall meet" should be replaced by "managers and workers are partners in the progress of business.

Workers Participation in Management has assumed great importance these days because it reduces industrial unrest and helps in dispelling employees misunderstanding about the outlook of management in industry. Workers participation has been found to have favorable effects on employee attitude, commitment and profitability even also on the efficiency of the management. Thus participative management should be seen as an inevitable tool in any organization. The management and worker have equal interests in the survival & the prosperity of the industry. It is also helpful to create peaceful and harmonious environment in the company and also helps in increasing the profitability in the company and also the workers participation in management improves understanding between managers and workers.

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